

Substitution Reaction of α -Haloester with Sulphur Nucleophiles

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THE reactivity of ethylbromoacetate with symmetrical diphenylthioureas has been measured conductometrically in methanol. Electron donating substituents in the phenyl groups enhance the rate. The reaction obeys Leffler's equation and fulfils Exner's criterion. The resonance and steric effects of various substituents have been evaluated. Solvent sensitivity with respect to both protic and dipolar aprotic solvents has been examined. The dipole moment of the solvent has been found to be the measure of true solvent polarity. This nucleophilic substitution reaction obeys most of the solvent properties in binary solvent mixture of methanol-water.

Thiazolidones are prepared by condensing phenylthioureas with α -haloesters¹. In continuation of our study on sulphur nucleophiles², the kinetics and mechanism of this well known reaction have been studied and are reported here.

Experimental

AnalaR grade methanol (S. Merck) was used as the main solvent. Other solvents were purified by standard method³. Triple distilled water was used for preparing binary solvent mixtures. The symmetrical diphenylthioureas were prepared and purified according to the method described earlier⁴. Ethylbromoacetate was a Fulka product. The procedure for rate measurement was the same as described elsewhere². The conductance measurements were made by Systronics conductance bridge at different intervals of time.

The product of the reaction was obtained by refluxing equimolar quantities of diphenylthiourea with ethylbromoacetate, m.p. 85°. It was identified to be 2-phenylimino-3-phenyl-4-thiazolidone [ir (cm⁻¹): 695 mono substitution benzene, 1630 -C=N, 1675 C=O five membered, 2850 CH₂ deformation in S-CH₂].

Results and Discussion

The rate constants at different temperatures and activation parameters are reported in Table I. The order of reactivity by introduction of different

substituents in the phenyl rings of thioureas is 4,4'-di-OC₂H₅ > 4,4'-di-CH₃ > 2,2'-di-OCH₃ > 3,3'-di-CH₃ > 4,4'-di-OCH₃ > 2,2'-di-CH₃ > H > 4,4'-di-Cl > 2,2'-di-Cl > 3,3'-di-Cl > 3,3'-di-NO₂ > 4,4'-di-carboxy. The rate pattern is in consonance with the nucleophilic attack of sulphur of thiourea on the methylene carbon holding the halogen. Both bonding and non-bonding effects contribute to the overall reaction mechanism.

The reaction is found to be energy and entropy dependent. A plot of $\Delta H^\ddagger$ vs $\Delta S^\ddagger$ is linear (gradient = 498.9 K). The energy and entropy changes can be explained in consideration of bending of bonds and rearrangement of solvent sheath in the cybotactic region. A compensation between the enthalpy and entropy terms indicates the operation of the same mechanism. This is further justified from the excellent linear relation between $\log k_{s,50}$ vs $\log k_{s,00}$ with unit slope, fulfilling Exner's⁵ criterion.

Since scattering of points was observed in a plot of $\log k$ vs σ , the inductive and resonance effects were calculated by the method of Taft and Lewis⁶. The ρ_I and α values are found to be -8.6 and 1.04, respectively at 35°. The value of α is consistent with the data observed in most of the bimolecular reactions. The values of resonance interaction energy and steric interaction energy for different substituents were evaluated (Table 2). In our earlier investigation² on the reaction of α -haloketone (phenacylbromide) with monoarylthioureas it was conclusively suggested that sulphur of thiourea acts as the nucleophile. The same arguments can also be extended for these diphenylthioureas. Based on the findings of the present investigation, the transition state (I) has been suggested for the reaction under investigation.

The kinetics of reaction of diphenylthiourea and its derivatives with ethylbromoacetate have also been studied in various protic and dipolar aprotic solvents. The results are reported in Table 3. The general effect of changing the solvent is to bring about a change in both E_a and $\log PZ$, the changes being in the same direction. The energy and entropy of activation values have been linearly fitted to the equation, $\Delta H^\ddagger = \Delta H^\ddagger_0 + \beta \Delta S^\ddagger$. So a compensation between activation parameters has been observed⁷. The value of gradient has been found to be 329.1 K. Two straight lines, one for protic and the other for dipolar aprotic solvent have been obtained by plotting⁸ $\log k_{s,50}$ vs $D - 1/2D + 1$. However, a plot of $\log k_{s,50}$ vs μ for both protic and dipolar aprotic solvents shows linearity. In

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NOTES

TABLE 1—THE RATE CONSTANTS AT VARIOUS TEMPERATURES AND ACTIVATION PARAMETERS FOR THE REACTION OF SUBSTITUTED PHENYLTHIOUREAS WITH ETHYLBROMOACETATE

Substituent in the phenyl ring (X)	$k_s \times 10^3 M^{-1} s^{-1}$					$\Delta H^\ddagger$ kJ mole ⁻¹	$\Delta G^\ddagger$ kJ mole ⁻¹	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$ J mole ⁻¹ K ⁻¹
	30	35	40	45	50°C			
4,4'-di-OC ₂ H ₅	10.12	16.32	20.75	35.22	49.79	60.11	86.5	85.71
4,4'-di-OH ₂	7.03	10.89	16.36	24.77	30.09	63.25	87.67	79.27
2,2'-di-OCH ₃	6.86	11.19	15.85	22.89	29.35	58.48	87.47	94.16
3,3'-di-CH ₃	6.66	10.41	14.06	19.49	28.55	55.01	87.63	105.90
4,4'-di-OCH ₃	6.48	8.70	12.65	18.33	27.22	68.98	88.13	62.87
2,2'-di-OH ₂	4.09	8.59	11.74	16.99	25.26	81.90	87.63	18.40
H	2.68	5.98	8.73	12.90	19.46	77.70	89.40	39.90
4,4'-di-Cl	2.48	3.09	4.63	8.14	10.57	71.4	90.77	62.95
2,2'-di-Cl	2.14	3.01	4.25	6.94	9.30	65.20	90.85	83.95
3,3'-di-Cl	1.89	2.32	3.38	5.66	8.93	71.11	91.61	66.30
3,3'-di-NO ₂	1.86	2.14	2.47	2.92	3.37	22.25	91.73	225.46
4,4'-di-carboxy	—	1.14	1.42	1.77	2.18	33.13	93.36	195.34

TABLE 2—INDUCTIVE (I) RESONANCE DUE TO META (R_m), RESONANCE DUE TO PARA (R_p), STERIC EFFECTS, RESONANCE AND STERIC INTERACTION ENERGY VALUES FOR THE REACTION BETWEEN ETHYLBROMOACETATE AND DIPHENYLTHIOUREAS IN METHANOL

Substituent	I	R _m	R _p	$\Delta\Delta F_m$ cal mole ⁻¹	$\Delta\Delta F_p$ cal mole ⁻¹	δE_s	$\Delta\Delta F_s$ cal mole ⁻¹
† Methoxy	-1.465	—	1.6737	—	-2.3738	0.1093	-0.1551
Methyl	0.4810	-0.1443	-0.1248	0.2047	0.1770	-0.0122	-0.0173
Chloro	-4.0514	3.6861	3.8106	-5.2288	-5.4048	-0.0114	-0.0162
Carboxy	-4.482	—	3.8085	—	-5.4020	—	—
Nitro	-5.4306	5.0302	—	-7.1355	—	—	—

TABLE 3—THE RATE CONSTANT AND ACTIVATION PARAMETERS FOR THE REACTION OF ETHYLBROMOACETATE WITH DIPHENYLTHIOUREAS IN DIFFERENT SOLVENTS

Solvent	$k_s \times 10^3 M^{-1} s^{-1}$					E_a kJ mole ⁻¹	log PZ	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$ J mole ⁻¹ k ⁻¹	$\Delta G^\ddagger$ kJ mole ⁻¹
	30	35	40	45	50°				
Methanol	2.68	5.38	8.73	12.9	19.46	75.1	11.27	39.90	89.4
Ethanol	4.7	5.94	10.69	16.16	23.67	70.35	9.20	69.31	89.1
Acetone	5.35	9.09	12.66	18.53	25.13	63.1	8.60	89.39	88.01
n-Propanol	—	10.40	16.89	23.60	32.59	59.48	8.49	91.52	87.67
Nitrobenzene	-1	13.20	23.88	39.38	65.70	87.63	12.90	6.50	87.05
DMSO	21.15	29.40	41.72	60.44	79.46	55.76	7.87	103.36	84.99

general, the rate increase is in consonance with the increase in dipole moment of the solvent. This conforms to the views of Benson⁹ that dipole moment of solvent can be considered as a measure of true solvent polarity.

The reaction was also studied in binary solvent mixture of methanol and water. The rate constants ($k_s \times 10^3 M^{-1} sec^{-1}$) at 35° are 5.38, 6.85, 6.94, 7.04 and 7.18 at 0, 5, 10, 15 and 20% water (v/v), respectively. The plot of the values of $\log k_{s,50}$ vs dielectric function, $D - 1/2D + 1$, in accordance with Krikwood expression is linear. When $\log k_{s,50}$ values are fitted to Grunwald-Winstein¹⁰ equation, a straight line is obtained with 'm' value of 0.37. The $\log k_{s,50}$ values plotted against Kosower 'Z' values¹¹ also show linearity. It seems, therefore, that the reaction under investigation obeys most of the solvent properties in aqueous solvent systems.

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